

Schumann resonance modes and ionosphere parameters: An annual variability comparison

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Abstract—Schumann Resonances (SR) result from an electromagnetic wave that propagates along the Earth-Ionosphere cavity. This signal is mainly characterized by the amplitude and frequency of the first modes; however, the relation with other variables that affect the Earth-ionosphere cavity is still undiscovered. In this paper, this relation is further explored with novel approaches supported by the usage of the first six Schumann Resonance modes and focusing on a different hour of the day. The relation is calculated using the correlation value between the monthly average of fifteen ionospheric variables and Schumann Resonance experimental values averaged by months and separated by hour. The result shows substantial support about the importance of aggregating all the information contained in the first six modes and also reinforces the previous evidence about the importance of separating Schumann Resonance variation by 24 hours to avoid mask effect produced by the daily variability. This work also provides new perspectives for predictors based on Schumann Resonance modes.

Index Terms—Schumann Resonance modes, Earth-ionosphere cavity, Lightning discharge, ionospheric variables, natural correlation

I. INTRODUCTION

SCHUMANN Resonances (SR) is the name given to the electromagnetic resonant phenomenon originated by the excitation of the earth ionosphere cavity [1], [2]. The earth-ionosphere wave guide cavity is formed by an insulator - the atmosphere - and two spherical media with a certain conductivity - the Earth's surface and the ionosphere's lower

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layer. The study of SR characterization has been widely addressed over the last 50 years. One common approach is to find models that match the experimental data recorded in different observatories over the world. [3], [4].

Other approaches are focused on establishing a possible link between SR variation and other natural phenomenon. It is broadly accepted that the main source of the cavity's excitation is the global lightning activity [5]. Therefore, one of the main subjects of study in the field of the SR has been the global thunderstorm centers, the name given to the three places on earth where lightning activity is highest at specific times of day [6]. The influence these thunderstorm centers have on SRs' hourly activity has been preliminary demonstrated [7]. Recently, a most detailed study of the correlation has been published [8], but the nuances of this interaction are yet to be uncovered. Recently, a work uses the 1st mode to estimate the global lightning activity [5]. There is also a completely documented relation between these parameters, focused on the 1st mode [9]. In this book, the authors establish the highest lighting activity as [7:00 - 13:00], [14:00 - 17:00], [20:00 - 2:00] Asian, African and American thunderstorm respectively.

Other studies have explored how SRs are influenced by the rest of environmental variables. One of the most popular examples is the relationship between peak intensity of the fundamental mode of SR and global temperature, which was proposed by [10]. A growing interest has been developed for studying the effect of earthquake activity on SRs, looking for an indicative that allows early detection [11], [12]. Nonetheless, most comparative studies of SR can be traced back to modifications in the ionosphere. From solar proton events [13], [14], Gamma rays [15], or even the seasonal and daily variations [16], all of these effects are related to modifications in the ionospheric conductivity profile.

It is also important to mention that the characterization gives useful insights about the variation of SR, specially in the frequencies values. These variations are mainly affected by meteorological factors, solar ionizing flux and solar wind condition [17]. The most studied periodic variations of the ionosphere are driven by the same periodical phenomena on the earth-sun: 11-year solar cycle, 27-day rotation and day-night cycle. The orientation of the Earth with respect to the sun causes local variations as well, with the most remarkable ones are being day night asymmetry and the seasonal asymmetry [18]. The latter is actually two-fold. First, there are discrepancies between hemispheres for a given moment in time and second, there are differences for any given season on each hemisphere as well, produced by the sun being closer to the

Earth during the northern hemisphere summer but farther away on the southern one [19]. These changes are still under study with the goal of finding an accurate predictor. New models has been proposed in order to improve the accuracy of the ionosphere variation prediction [20].

It is also important to mention the natural relation between the height of the ionosphere and lightning activity. Lightning activity is more intense when the ionosphere is very close to the earth and it leads to a change in the ionosphere cavity [21].

Many studies have been carried out for understanding the relation between SRs' frequency and condition of the lower ionosphere. In [22], the author explains the dependency of SR modes and the vertical profile of the ionosphere. In [23] the very low frequency (VLF) band is used to study the characteristics of the ionosphere due to the frequency dependency of the ionosphere conductivity. Another author [24] also uses the extremely low frequency (ELF) band to monitor the height of the D-layer. In this paper, the researchers use a reflection height dependent on the frequency.

It is possible to conclude that SR variability and ionospheric variables have been individually analyzed and also studied in regard to the SR relation with a particular ionosphere variable, with a very specific approach. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is a lack of a research which the focus on studying the interaction between multiple ionospheric variable and their relation with different SR modes. Exploiting all the data available will provide valuable insight in the study of SR.

There are two facts that give way for improvement and development of a methodology that may fulfill the requirements for this study.

First, due to the fact that the propagation characteristic in a complex cavity is highly dependent of the signal frequency, the information contained in each SR mode can have substantial differences. Although there are several studies about the relationship between SR and ionospheric variability [8], [13], [25], [26], most of them consider only the fundamental mode, missing the possible information that other SR modes provide.

Secondly, most studies have tended to focus on the relation between ionosphere long-term variability and SR variations by averaging daily values [6], [27]. Although this approach is entirely valid and has produced many valuable results, it suffers from the analysis of the long-term relation for specific hours, which are not masked by the day to day variability. It is also important to notice that since SR are partly defined by the ionospheric conductivity profile, ionospheric variations should be reflected in SR records. Nonetheless, when accounting all the parameters that usually define the conductivity profile of the ionosphere, a new approach is clearly needed, one that analyzes which variable is responsible for a specific behavior.

By taking into account all measurable modes and working with hourly averaged frequency for each one, its comparison with the most relevant parameters that affect the ionosphere composition would yield the mode and hour where each ionospheric parameter influences SR the most. Although SR response depends on the general state of the ionosphere, certain ionospheric parameters may be dominant at certain times of the day, for certain modes. Thus, by cross-correlating hourly averaged activity with ionospheric data, strong correlations

may indicate which parameters are dominant at specific hours and over which SR modes. In other words, finding an hour in which the activity of a particular parameter of the ionosphere rules out the rest implies that there is no other relevant effect in the electromagnetic cavity that could obscure its impact in the SR frequency variation records. frequency variation records. By tracking this hour along different years, it would be possible to see a similar pattern between this effect and the variability of the SR mode. As a base to test this hypothesis, this paper will investigate the relation between ionosphere parameters variability over the 5-year period from 2016 to 2020 in comparison with the first six modes of the SR during the same period of time.

II. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The data used in this research along with a brief explanation about the proposed methodology is exposed in this section.

A. Ionosphere Data

The number of sunspots has been obtained from [28]:

- **Sunspots - (sunspot):** Classical measure of the solar power emitted - events per day.
- **Northern Hemisphere Sunspots - (sunspotN):** Classical measure of the solar power emitted - Northern hemisphere.
- **Southern Hemisphere Sunspots - (sunspotS):** Classical measure of the solar power emitted - Southern Hemisphere.

Solar Flux [29] is the electromagnetic power received by the sun per surface unit measured in $1 \times 10^{-22} \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ Hz})$:

- **Adjusted Solar Flux (SolarFlux):** Standard method for estimate the real solar flux from the observable measurement of the magnetic flux received on the Earth's surface.

Layer height from GYRO [30]. The values are the minimum virtual height [F/F2/E/Es] traces measured in km. A complete description about the ionosphere layer composition can be found in [31]:

- **Sporadic E Layer (hEs):** The result of wind shears, meteors and other phenomena.
- **E Layer (hE):** Particles ionized due to soft X-ray (1–10 nm) and UV.
- **F1 Layer (hF1):** Strongly affected by the solar radiation.
- **F2 Layer (hF2):** Variations are usually large, irregular, and particularly pronounced during magnetic storms.

Geomagnetic indexes from [32]:

- **Geomagnetic Index Kp (Kp):** The K-index is quasi-logarithmic local index of the 3-hourly range in magnetic activity relative to an assumed quiet-day curve for a single geomagnetic observatory site.
- **Geomagnetic index Ap (Ap):** The Ap-index is defined as the earliest occurring maximum 24-hour value obtained by computing an 8-point running average of successive 3-hour ap indices during a geomagnetic storm event and is uniquely associated with the storm event.

Quantity of electrons in the ionosphere from GYRO [30]:

- **Total Electron Content (TEC)** $1 \times 10^{-16} \text{ m}^{-2}$. Highly dependent of Solar Flux.

Total number of Lighting measured in US [33]:

- **Lightning Activity (Lightning)**: Strikes per day.

Averaged temperature extracted from [34] using the last improvements, as explained in [35]:

- **Global Temperature (Temp)**: Global temperature anomaly measured in degrees.

Characterization of the D layer obtained using the software international Reference Ionosphere (IRI2016) based on [36]:

- **Simulated TEC in D layer (TEC-D)**: The data unit is in $1 \times 10^{-16} \text{ m}^{-2}$.

B. Schumann Resonance Data

SR data has been recorded continuously since 2015 at the Sierra de Filabres observatory in Almería, Spain. The data is captured in 30-minutes registers by two perpendicular sensors, one oriented North-South and other East-West. Each file is processed using a transform to the frequency domain, and a fit to a sum of Lorentzian functions. After the fitting process, the extraction of the peak frequency and intensity for each mode is obtained. A more detailed explanation of the process and the day-to-day variability can be found in [16] for the years 2016 and 2017.

In the present work, the results are obtained from 1st January of 2016 to 31st December of 2020.

C. Methodology

The present study is focused on tracking changes in the ionosphere by means of the SR variations, in a way where the most number of variables can be accounted for. As advanced in Section I, this analysis is based on the hypothesis that the ionospheric parameter that affects one or more SR modes the most changes over time. Consequently, by extracting the hourly averaged peak frequency for each of the first six modes and grouping them by the hour of the day, we could verify through cross-correlation at which hour a specific mode shows the same tendency as a certain ionospheric parameter.

To implement the idea above and shape the analysis, data has been reprocessed as follows:

- 1) Data is divided by hours, and the frequency spectrum of each segment is extracted from the SR records.
- 2) Each of the produced frequency registers contains the hourly average peak frequency of each mode up to the sixth. From each month and each mode, the values above are further averaged, producing 24 hourly averaged peak frequency by month for each mode.
- 3) The ionosphere parameters described above are treated to homogenize them.

From there, each dataset produced for each hour and each mode is cross-correlated with every dataset from the parameters of the ionosphere. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r), using Eq. 1 gives us an indication on how closely the measured peak frequency on that hour follows the ionospheric parameter's variations, where x and y represent the two variables under study.

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

An example of this process can be seen on Fig. 1. The data depicted in Fig 1a obtained a high and negative correlation value. Fig 1b showed a low correlation value. For each correlation, a student's T test is performed to assess its viability. The results of this test are considered along with the correlation coefficients to determine the validity of the results.

This study is performed on data from the period from 2016 to 2020, having full data registers for both the SRs and the ionosphere parameters. Given the above, this means 24 peak values for each 60 months for each of the first six modes of the SR for the NS mode and Frequency variation value, leading to a total of 24 hours \times 6 modes datasets of 60 months.

Fig. 1. 5-years time comparison between the Ionosphere parameters and SR mode frequency variation. (a) SR mode 4 at 11:00 and E layer Height. $r = -0.8, p = 10^{-13.9}$. (b) SR mode 1 at 11:00 and Total Electron Count. $r = 0, p = 1$.

III. RESULTS

In this section we present the results obtained by correlating the ionosphere variables under study with the data obtained in our observatory. The hours expressed in the result are all refers to the UTC timezone. We have focused on the North-South sensor and the frequency variation mainly for two reasons. First, frequency variation is quite dependent on the conductive properties of the electromagnetic cavity on a given moment, so analyzing a single channel is enough to test the methodology, which is the goal of this article. Second, analyzing both channels would duplicate the amount of information to show, and given the high amount of variables involved in this work we consider it would dilute the results more than reinforce them. Therefore, we have chosen to limited the presented result to the N-S channel.

A. Total relevant hours

Table I summarizes the results of the cross-correlation between SRs' modes and ionosphere parameters. There are two values for each mode and ionosphere parameter; total number of hours for which the Pearson correlation p-value is under 0.01 (left) and the averaged Pearson correlation coefficient for those hours (right). If no hour had a significant p-value for a given mode and parameter, the cell is left blank.

The height parameters will be presented. The lower layer of the ionosphere - **D layer** - has an important factor of correlation with the 2nd, 3rd and 4th mode. The next **E and Es layers** display a similar behavior but less related to the second mode and more with the 4th and 5th modes. **F layer** breaks the pattern above, with the highest number of hours belonging to the 1st mode and showing no relationship with the 6th. On the contrary, **F2 Layer** has the highest number of hours on which the correlation is significant, and higher correlation

coefficients than the rest of layers. This is surprising since this layer is mostly relevant during the night hours. It is also the layer better correlated with the 5th and 6th modes.

TABLE I

SUM OF TOTAL HOUR WITH A CORRELATION -VALUE LOWER THAN 0.01, FIRST: NUMBER OF HOURS, SECOND: MEAN CORRELATION.

	Mode 1	Mode 2	Mode 3	Mode 4	Mode 5	Mode 6
hD	9 - 42%	16 - 58%	20 - 65%	16 - 62%	13 - 49%	11 - 53%
hE	10 - 42%	13 - 50%	18 - 65%	17 - 62%	5 - 51%	10 - 54%
hEs	10 - 42%	14 - 50%	19 - 61%	16 - 62%	5 - 47%	10 - 51%
hF	14 - 41%	8 - 52%	11 - 40%	8 - 40%	4 - 36%	2 - 36%
hF2	14 - 45%	17 - 59%	20 - 67%	17 - 64%	13 - 56%	10 - 58%
TEC	11 - 43%	10 - 54%	14 - 56%	13 - 51%	3 - 42%	9 - 40%
sunspot	23 - 55%	14 - 43%	11 - 41%	6 - 41%		2 - 37%
sunspotN	20 - 52%	14 - 41%	4 - 48%	1 - 50%		2 - 41%
sunspotS	21 - 44%	4 - 46%	9 - 40%	4 - 47%	8 - 37%	
Kp	21 - 59%	6 - 48%	2 - 44%	4 - 43%		
Ap	22 - 58%	6 - 46%	3 - 42%	4 - 43%	1 - 34%	
Lightning	7 - 44%	18 - 61%	20 - 57%	16 - 56%	16 - 49%	10 - 56%
Temp			4 - 35%	2 - 38%	5 - 39%	4 - 43%
SolarFlux	19 - 52%	11 - 41%	8 - 42%	5 - 43%		1 - 34%

Regarding **TEC**, the relation with almost all modes is clear, showing significant correlations for an average of 11 hours in except with this 5th mode on which it only correlates for 3 hours, and with not a too high value of correlation. For the rest of *Schumann Resonance* (SR) modes, the mode with the most significant correlations is the 3rd, with 14 hours, and the one with the less is the 6th with 9.

Sunspot values (both total - **sunspot** - and separated by hemisphere - **sunspotN** and **sunspotS**) show a clear correlation with the first mode, in which almost all hours of the day are significant. The presence of this dependency decreases in the higher SR modes, with only 6 hours showing a significant correlation in the 4th mode and absent in the 5th. Although two hours correlated significantly with the 6th mode, the correlation coefficient is very low. Northern sunspots display a correlation with the 2nd mode similar to the one of global sunspots, whereas the southern sunspots are only significant during four hours. That being said, southern sunspots have more hours for the rest of modes than the northern, showing similarities in tendency even with the 5th mode, but once again with a low correlation coefficient.

The geomagnetic indexes, **Kp** and **Ap**, seem to have a high influence over the 1st mode, with the highest average correlation coefficient for this mode and all hours of the day except two being significant. However, this relation is not observable for the rest of modes. Both indexes display a very similar behavior, which is to be expected given the way **Ap** index is directly derived from **Kp**.

The daily mean of **Lightning** discharges displays a strong relationship with the 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th mode. The relation is also relevant for the 6th mode. Contrary to the rest of the parameters, the lowest average correlation coefficient of this variable belongs to the 1st mode. The number of significant hours is also lower on this mode than on the rest.

Global temperature (**Temp**) is not very relevant for any of the SR modes, specially for the first two modes, in which no hour displays a correlation whose significance goes above the

specified threshold. Although this result may result surprising and against the accepted literature [10], it is important to remark that the relation under study is focused on frequency variations, while most of the previous studies that explored the relation between global temperature and SR are centered in the intensity variations of the latter.

Solar magnetic Flux (**SolarFlux**) correlates significantly with the 1st mode for 19 hours off the day, with an average correlation coefficient of 52% which is worthy of attention. The number of significant hours for the rest of modes is considerably lower, decreasing as the mode order increases and disappearing in the 5th mode. Average correlation coefficients for these modes are also lower than the one obtained for the 1st but consistent, being around 42%.

B. Hour Correlation

The results are summarized in a set of heatmap. Each heatmap is composed by the values of the correlation between the ionospheric variable under study and the evolution of the SR mode at an specific hour. Each column represents a particular SR mode while the rows are for the hour of the day of the selected SR mode. Colors express the intensity of the correlation as well as the sign. Red colours are for a high positive correlation and blue colours for the negative one. As expected, different patterns emerge from the correlation between SR peak frequency modes by hours and the evolution of each ionosphere parameter, which provides considerable insight into the relationship between them. However, this analysis offers preliminary evidence for the relation between a specific time interval of the SR mode with a particular parameter of the ionosphere. In the following, the relation between each mode and the ionosphere parameters will be studied in depth.

1) *Ionosphere Virtual Height*. The patterns mentioned above can be clearly observed in Fig. 2, where the most relevant hours shift for each modes and layer, but with an observable relationship between them. It can be observed that the **E and Es layers** layers have an almost completely identical pattern. The 1st mode is positively correlated at 11:00 and negative at 6:00. However, this correlation is far lower than with the rest of the mode. It can be seen that a negative correlation expands around 12:00 in the higher modes, starting with an interval of 2 hours in the 2nd mode, 6 hours in the 3rd mode and 8 hours in the 4th mode. Surprisingly, in the 5th mode it is not possible to see this pattern while the 6th mode returns to this behavior.

The next layer, **F layer**, shows an important positive correlation for the hours between 23:00 and 6:00 in the 1st mode, whereas the 2nd mode mirrors the 1st, having its peak correlation value when the 1st mode is at its lowest and vice versa. For the rest of the hours and SR modes, there is not a clear tendency. For the **F2 layer**, the same behavior is clear as for the **E and Es layers** however it is inverted. To expose the differences between these layers, during the interval from 8:00 to 15:00, the **F2 layer** shows a higher intensity of the correlation and the number of hours with this correlation than **E and Es layers**. In the same way, the negative correlation appearing in the **F layer** for the hours 22:00 to 2:00 in the

Fig. 2. Pearson Correlation coefficient between SR modes and ionosphere Height measurement, separated by hours. The Y-axis represents the time interval selected for the SR peak frequency mode. The X-axis represents the SR mode selected. (a) Virtual Height of The Sporadic E ionosphere Layer (b) Virtual Height of The E ionosphere Layer (c) Virtual Height of The F ionosphere Layer (d) Virtual Height of the Sporadic F2 ionosphere Layer.

2nd and 3rd mode appears as positive in **E and Es layers**.

2) *Ionosphere Electron Content D layer*. The lowest layer of the ionosphere, **D layer**, is not continuously measured and the simulation has to be performed to obtain the time variation characteristic. The correlation between the simulated electron content of the **D layer** and hourly SR frequency mode variation is shown in Fig. 3. Unexpectedly, the results of this layer are very close to the result for the **F2 layer**, although there is a large difference in distance between them.

Apart from that, there are minor differences in the intensity of some hours. For example in the SR mode 1:00 at 6:00, the correlation value is significantly higher for this layer than the F2. The higher values of F2 with the 3rd mode are also noticeable. One of the most striking results to emerge from the data related to the Ionosphere layers is that the correlation is far more intense during the central hours - 10:00 to 16:00 just for the upper SR mode, specifically for the 3rd and 4th modes, and not with the 1st mode. This aspect will be discussed in detail in the discussion section.

3) *Total Lighting Discharges*. In Fig.4, the correlation can be observed. For the 1st mode, the values are considerably lower than for the rest of the modes. In 2nd mode, there are three main intervals with very high values, two with a negative

Fig. 3. Pearson Correlation coefficient between SR modes and ionosphere Height measurement, separated by hours. The Y-axis represents the time interval selected for the SR peak frequency mode. The X-axis represents the SR mode selected. Number of Electrons in D layer (Simulated - IRI2016).

correlation: from 22:00 to 4:00 and from 16:00 to 18:00, and one with positive: from 11:00 to 12:00. The most striking part is related to the interval between 16:00 and 18:00, this correlation is neither present in any other mode nor for other ionosphere variable. For the rest of the SR modes, the pattern

is very similar to the previous comment for the **D** layer, with the exception of lower correlation values during the central hours, and higher during the night hours. It is also important to notice the high value of the 6thth modes during central hours, higher than in the previously commented ionosphere variables.

Fig. 4. Pearson Correlation coefficient between SR modes and ionosphere Height measurement, separated by hours. The Y-axis represents the time interval selected for the SR peak frequency mode. The X-axis represents the SR mode selected. and y-axis: Lightning Discharges.

4) *Global Temperature Anomaly.* Unlike other research carried out in the area, we did not find a significant relation between global temperature anomaly and SR modes frequency variation. The low values of the correlation can be seen in Fig. 5. The highest values of correlation appear in the 3rd mode, for 5 hours, and with a not very relevant value of 40% approximately.

Fig. 5. Pearson Correlation coefficient between SR modes and ionosphere Height measurement, separated by hours. The Y-axis represents the time interval selected for the SR peak frequency mode. The X-axis represents the SR mode selected. and y-axis: Temperature anomaly.

5) *Solar Magnetic Flux and Total Electron Content.* In Fig.6, the estimate magnetic flux from the sun and the **TEC** can be seen. These two ionospheric variables show a strong relation for the 1st mode.

Fig. 6. Pearson Correlation coefficient between SR modes and ionosphere Height measurement, separated by hours. The Y-axis represents the time interval selected for the SR peak frequency mode. The X-axis represents the SR mode selected. (a) Solar Flux Adjusted, (b) Estimate Total Electron count.

In the case of the Solar Flux, this relation lasts from 18:00 to 7:00, while for the **TEC** it is shorter, from 2:00 to 6:00. For the rest of the modes, there is not high correlation for the Solar Flux, except at 22:00 in the 4th mode. However, the **TEC** exposes a total different behavior, with a very strong relation for the 2nd, 3rd and 4th modes. It is also interesting that high values are obtained between 18:00 and 19:00 for the 3rd mode. All the correlations with these two variables are just positive.

6) *Geomagnetic Index and Total Number of sunspot.* In Fig. 7, the relation between the geometric index and total sunspot can be seen. The geometric index **Kp** and hemispheres sunspot have been omitted because it shows the same pattern in this graphs than the respective ionosphere variables. The results show a very important relation between this two ionosphere variables and the 1st mode, with a high value of correlation which lasts around 12 hours for the geometric index **Ap** and 16 hours for sunspot. It is also important to notice two intervals in the sunspot case: for the 3rd mode, there is a high value at 18:00 and another in the 4th mode at 22:00. There are not clear correlations with the rest of the modes.

All the previously commented figures have been summa-

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. Pearson Correlation coefficient between SR modes and ionosphere Height measurement, separated by hours. The Y-axis represents the time interval selected for the SR peak frequency mode. The X-axis represents the SR mode selected. (a) Ap geometric index, (b) Sunspots count in both hemispheres.

alized in Table II. This table exposed the most correlated intervals for each parameters and for the six first modes. In this table the p-value maximum is 0.001. Therefore, the values of the correlation are considerable higher than in the previous table.

IV. DISCUSSION

The relation between some of the most relevant ionosphere parameters and SR frequency peak variation has been studied. This result offers valuable insight into the relation between SR modes and specific ionosphere parameters. This underlines just how important is the SR mode in relation with the ionosphere. It is clear that not all Ionosphere parameters affects in the same way to each SR mode.

Even though the results obtained in this paper differ from previous studies [10], it provides a valuable information. The relation with the first mode is not the expected, while the relation with the higher modes is clearly satisfactory with previous evidences [9]. There are clearly 3 intervals, one positive from 16:00 to 20:00 which is similar to African thunderstorm, another from 21:00 to 3:00 which is very close to the American thunderstorm and the third, positive, from

TABLE II
MAJOR CORRELATION INTERVALS WITH MEAN VALUE IN %FOR THE IONOSPHERE VARIABLES UNDER STUDIES FOR EACH OF THE FIRST SIX SCHUMANN RESONANCE MODES.

	Mode 1	Mode 2	Mode 3	Mode 4	Mode 5	Mode 6
hF	[23- 7] 50	[8-14] 58	[10-12] 43 [14-16] 48	[9-12] 44		
hF2	[6- 7] 42 [9-14] -52 [16-19] -50	[7-14] 56 [16-18] -50 [22- 5] -67	[6-16] 73 [19-20] 45 [21- 4] -71	[4- 5] -54 [6-17] 71 [21-22] -44 [23- 2] -55	[6- 7] 45 [8-13] 64 [16-17] 47 [18-20] 53 [22- 2] -52	[8-14] 61 [15-17] 68
hE	[6- 7] -49 [10-13] 49	[10-13] -57 [16-17] 45 [23- 5] 54	[6-16] -64 [21- 4] 65	[4- 5] 54 [6-17] -72 [19-20] -53 [24- 1] 42	[9-12] -52 [18-19] -56	[8-13] -60 [15-17] -61
hEs	[6- 7] -49 [9-12] 50	[11-13] -62 [16-17] 50 [23- 5] 53	[7-16] -64 [21- 4] 65	[4- 5] 57 [7-17] -72 [19-20] -49 [24- 2] 43	[9-11] -52 [18-19] -57	[9-13] -62 [15-17] -59
tec	[21-22] 43 [23- 8] 47	[7-15] 55 [20-22] 46	[5-16] 58 [18-20] 60	[6-14] 56 [15-16] 50 [19-20] 47	[9-10] 48	[12-13] 46 [15-16] 47
sunspot	[14-15] 44 [18-11] 64	[14-16] 44 [18-23] 48	[17-20] 53	[21-23] 53		
sunspotN	[18-11] 56	[8- 9] 42 [13-16] 45 [19-22] 47	[17-20] 53	[22-23] 50		[1- 2] -44
sunspotS	[5- 6] 44 [8-11] 49 [19-20] 49 [21- 3] 55	[21-23] 50	[20-23] 46	[20-23] 51	[23- 0] 41	
Kp	[14-15] 48 [16-11] 59	[18-23] 50	[17-19] 44	[18-19] 44 [22-23] 52		
Ap	[14-15] 47 [16-11] 59	[18-23] 48	[17-19] 46	[18-19] 46 [22-23] 41		
Lightning	[10-13] -48 [16-18] -49	[9-13] 54 [16-19] -64 [22- 6] -71	[6- 8] 44 [9-13] 59 [14-16] 53 [17-18] -44 [20- 4] -65	[3- 5] -59 [6- 7] 47 [9-14] 59 [15-17] 52 [23- 2] -70	[9-12] 59 [16-17] 50 [18-20] 50 [22- 2] -61	[8-14] 59 [15-17] 62
Temp		[1- 3] 43 [4- 5] 42 [16-18] 43	[17-18] 45 [23- 4] 49	[1- 2] 42 [16-17] -46	[19-21] -46	[10-12] -51 [19-20] -45
SolarFlux	[10-11] 49 [18- 9] 57	[9-11] 43 [12-13] 42 [20-22] 49	[16-20] 48	[21-23] 53		
hD	[5- 7] 51 [11-13] -43 [17-18] -44	[7-14] 61 [23- 4] -65	[5-16] 72 [18-20] 53 [21- 4] -56	[4- 5] -42 [6-17] 72 [19-20] 42 [24- 1] -51	[8-12] 64 [18-20] 45 [22- 2] -45	[8-14] 57 [15-17] 64

10:00 to 12:00, matching with the Asian thunderstorm center. These three correlation values in these intervals are very high during the 2nd mode. In the higher SR mode, the interval of the African thunderstorm disappears, the American one, lower their value and is not present in the 6th mode, while the positive interval, the American one increases the value and the number of hours.

As stated at the start of this section, a strong relationship between the 1st mode and the lightning activity was to be expected [6]. Despite having significant correlation values at some hours, these are not as clear as those shown in the rest of modes. In line with the initial hypothesis of this work, the lessened correlation of the 1st mode with the lightning activity is pointing out how frequency variations in this mode are far more sensitive to changes in other parameters, for example the solar flux.

The virtual height of the ionosphere is a characteristic which summarizes the electron content of this layer [5]. From a theoretical point of view, when the ionosphere layer has a lower value, the cavity reduces their boundary condition so the time to reach the whole cavity increases, then the frequency

decreases. When the SR mode depends on an specific layer, it is expected to increase their frequency value when the height is lower.

The correlations shown in Section III are in good agreement with the studies previously mentioned. For the **E and Es layer**, the correlation is negative and near 70%. These layers are the lowest part of the ionosphere. It can be seen how 1st mode dependency with these layers is not quite strong, except at 6:00 and 11:00. These two hours are significant, since, by looking at other results, it is plainly clear that this SR mode has no other important correlation at these hours. This supports the grounds on which this work is based; at these hours, frequency variations on the 1st mode are mostly the result of the influences of the height on **E and Es layers**. The close relation between the sixth modes and lighting activity can be noticed in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Time evolution of the SR peak frequency mode at 11:00 and the total lightning discharges between 2016 and 2020. (a) 1st mode. (b) 2nd mode. (c) 3rd mode. (d) 4th mode. (e) 5th mode. (f) 6th mode.

In the central hours, the correlation for almost all modes is negative, while at nighttime it is positive. It is important to mark that **E Layer** is mainly important during day hours. However, due to the power line leakage in the 6th mode, the result of this mode presents a major source of unreliability. Contrary to expectations, **F2 layer** height and Electron content of the **D layer** behavior is the opposite of what was expected. It can be seen how when the virtual height of this layer increases, the higher modes' frequency also increases. In contrast, in the **F2 layer**, the 1st mode is very dependent with the relation previously mentioned. During the central hours it can be established that the 1st mode has a boundary condition mostly related to the **F2 layer**. Therefore, observing **F layer**, during the nighttime the 1st mode is closely related to the **F layer**. It can be explained by the asymmetries of the ionosphere around

the globe. This relation is not present for the Electron content of the **D layer**, although it has a strong correlation at 6:00.

One of the most remarkable advances in SR studies was the link between SR and the Global Tropical Temperature by Williams et al [10]. We have studied the relation between frequency variation and the temperature anomaly values. However, our results do not give a clear link between these two variables. It could be explained by the fact that our analysis is mainly focused on the frequency variation and finding a pattern which repeats over the 4 years, which is not the case of the global temperature. In the higher modes, it is possible to see some high values around midnight for the 2nd and 3rd modes.

The **Magnetic Solar Flux** is the main source of ionization for the ionosphere [31]. Nowadays, it is possible to monitor the solar flux while historically this function was done by counting sunspots. In this paper, we have presented these three forms, i.e. Solar flux, Geometric index **Ap** and also sunspot. We can see that this parameter can be used to study the 1st mode. To the best of our knowledge, this relationship has not been exposed or theorized in the literature, and explaining it thoroughly is out of the scope of this article. Nonetheless, we can propose a couple of mechanisms that may explain it. SR energy is mainly focused on the first resonance due to the attenuation factor which depends on SR mode frequency. These ionosphere parameters determine the baseline of the SR propagation and inject the energy for the lightning activity. That being said, further research is needed to characterize this relationship properly.

TEC is only important for the first mode during the interval from 0:00 to 7:00 and also during central hours for the 2nd, 3rd, 4th modes, due to the difference with other patterns, which need to be interpreted with attention in order to find a possible explanation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

To sum up, we have proposed a novel methodology for studying the correlation between some of the most important ionospheric parameters and SR frequency variation for the first six modes. This methodology has been used for analyzing the SR data from the Almeria Sierra de Filabres observatory (Spain) in the period from 2016 to 2020. Evidence from this study points out how these parameters' effect over each SR mode changes hourly, hence provides valuable insight to the hypothesis of different ionospheric parameters being more relevant for different modes at different hours. We have obtained comprehensive results, indicating that the affectation of SR frequency from the ionosphere is not homogeneous for all the SR modes. The present findings might suggest several courses of action, in order to develop a computational model for predicting the variability of the earth ionosphere using a combination of the frequency variability in different SR modes separated by the hour of the day.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. O. Schumann, "Über die strahlungslosen Eigenschwingungen einer leitenden Kugel, die von einer Luftschicht und einer Ionosphärenhülle umgeben ist," *Zeitschrift für Naturforschung - Section A Journal of Physical Sciences*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 149–154, 1952.

- [2] T. Madden and W. Thompson, "Low frequency electromagnetic oscillations of the Earth-ionosphere cavity," *Reviews of Geophysics*, vol. 3, no. May, 1965. [Online]. Available: <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/RG003i002p00211/full>
- [3] E. S. Goncharov, A. N. Lyakhov, and T. V. Loseva, "3D-FEM simulation model of the Earth-ionosphere cavity," *Journal of Electromagnetic Waves and Applications*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 734–742, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/09205071.2019.1575289>
- [4] C. Kwisanga and C. J. Fourie, "3-D modeling of electromagnetic wave propagation in the uniform earth-ionosphere cavity using a commercial FDTD software package," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 65, no. 6, pp. 3275–3278, 2017.
- [5] E. Prácer, T. Bozöki, G. Satori, E. Williams, A. Guha, and H. Yu, "Reconstruction of Global Lightning Activity Based on Schumann Resonance Measurements: Model Description and Synthetic Tests," *Radio Science*, vol. 54, no. 3, pp. 254–267, 2019.
- [6] A. V. Koloskov, A. P. Nickolaenko, Y. M. Yampolsky, C. Hall, and O. V. Budanov, "Variations of global thunderstorm activity derived from the long-term Schumann resonance monitoring in the Antarctic and in the Arctic," *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, vol. 201, no. February, p. 105231, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jastp.2020.105231>
- [7] M. Soler-Ortiz, M. F. Ros, N. N. Castellano, and J. A. Parra, "A new way of analyzing the schumann resonances: A statistical approach," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 70, 2021.
- [8] G. Tatsis, A. Sakkas, V. Christofilakis, G. Baldoumas, S. K. Chronopoulos, A. K. Paschalidou, P. Kassomenos, I. Petrou, P. Kostarakis, C. Repapis, and V. Tritakis, "Correlation of local lightning activity with extra low frequency detector for schumann resonance measurements," *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 787, 2021.
- [9] A. Nickolaenko and M. Hayakawa, *Schumann resonance for tyros: Essentials of global electromagnetic resonance in the earth-ionosphere cavity*. Springer, Tokyo, 2014.
- [10] E. R. Williams, "The schumann resonance: A global tropical thermometer," *Science*, 1992.
- [11] K. Florios, I. Contopoulos, V. Christofilakis, G. Tatsis, S. Chronopoulos, C. Repapis, and V. Tritakis, "Pre-seismic Electromagnetic Perturbations in Two Earthquakes in Northern Greece," *Pure and Applied Geophysics*, vol. 177, no. 2, pp. 787–799, 2020.
- [12] J. A. Gazquez, R. M. Garcia, N. N. Castellano, M. Fernandez-Ros, A. J. Perea-Moreno, and F. Manzano-Agugliaro, "Applied engineering using Schumann Resonance for earthquakes monitoring," *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, vol. 7, no. 11, 2017.
- [13] M. Sanfui and D. Biswas, "First mode Schumann resonance frequency variation during a solar proton event," *Terrestrial, Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 253–259, 2016.
- [14] I. G. Kudintseva, S. A. Nikolayenko, A. P. Nickolaenko, and M. Hayakawa, "Schumann resonance background signal synthesized in time," *Telecommunications and Radio Engineering (English translation of *Elektrosvyaz and Radiotekhnika*)*, vol. 76, no. 9, pp. 807–825, 2017.
- [15] A. P. Nickolaenko, I. G. Kudintseva, O. Pechony, M. Hayakawa, Y. Hobaru, and Y. T. Tanaka, "The effect of a gamma ray flare on schumann resonances," *Annales Geophysicae*, vol. 30, pp. 1321–1329, 2012.
- [16] C. Cano-Domingo, M. Fernandez-Ros, N. Novas, and J. A. Gazquez, "Diurnal and seasonal results of the Schumann Resonance Observatory in Sierra de Filabres, Spain," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, no. 1962, pp. 1–10, 2021.
- [17] J. M. Forbes, S. E. Palo, and X. Zhang, "Variability of the ionosphere," *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, vol. 62, no. 8, pp. 685–693, 2000.
- [18] T. Dang, W. Wang, A. Burns, X. Dou, W. Wan, and J. Lei, "Simulations of the ionospheric annual asymmetry: Sun-Earth distance effect," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, vol. 122, no. 6, pp. 6727–6736, 2017.
- [19] Y. Jin and C. Xiong, "Interhemispheric Asymmetry of Large-Scale Electron Density Gradients in the Polar Cap Ionosphere: UT and Seasonal Variations," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, vol. 125, no. 2, 2020.
- [20] X. BIN and Y. LIU, "Improved model of ionosphere variability and study for long-term statistical characteristics," *Chinese Journal of Aeronautics*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 407–419, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cja.2020.03.018>
- [21] M. Friedrich and M. Rapp, "News from the lower ionosphere: A review of recent developments," *Surveys in Geophysics*, vol. 30, pp. 525–559, 2009.
- [22] A. P. Nickolaenko, Y. P. Galuk, and M. Hayakawa, "Vertical profile of atmospheric conductivity that matches Schumann resonance observations," *SpringerPlus*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–12, 2016.
- [23] K. L. Koh, Z. Liu, and M. Füllekrug, "Lower Ionosphere Effects on Narrowband Very Low Frequency Transmission Propagation: Fast Variabilities and Frequency Dependence," *Radio Science*, vol. 53, no. 5, pp. 611–623, 2018.
- [24] M. Füllekrug, A. C. Fraser-Smith, and K. Schlegel, "Global ionospheric D-layer height monitoring," *Europhysics Letters*, vol. 59, no. 4, pp. 626–632, 2002.
- [25] A. Pizzuti, A. Bennett, and M. Füllekrug, "Long-term observations of schumann resonances at portishead (uk)," *Atmosphere*, vol. 13, 1 2022.
- [26] P. S. Figueredo, B. M. Ortega, M. Pazos, D. R. Osorio, E. A. Mascote, V. M. Mendoza, and R. Garduño, "Schumann resonance anomalies possibly associated with large earthquakes in mexico," *Indian Journal of Physics*, vol. 95, pp. 1959–1966, 10 2021.
- [27] X. Y. Ouyang, Z. Xiao, Y. Q. Hao, and D. H. Zhang, "Variability of schumann resonance parameters observed at low latitude stations in china," *Advances in Space Research*, vol. 56, pp. 1389–1399, 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2015.07.006>
- [28] F. Clette and L. Lefèvre, "The New Sunspot Number: Assembling All Corrections," *Solar Physics*, vol. 291, no. 9–10, pp. 2629–2651, 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11207-016-1014-y>
- [29] K. F. Tapping, "The 10.7 cm solar radio flux (F10.7)," *Space Weather*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 394–406, 2013.
- [30] B. W. Reinisch and I. A. Galkin, "Global ionospheric radio observatory (GIRO)," *Earth, Planets and Space*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 377–381, 2011.
- [31] K. Rawer, *Wave propagation in the ionosphere*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2013, vol. 5.
- [32] J. Matzka, C. Stolle, Y. Yamazaki, O. Bronkalla, and A. Morschhauser, "The geomagnetic kp index and derived indices of geomagnetic activity," *Space Weather*, vol. 19, pp. 1–21, 2021.
- [33] D. J. Cecil, D. E. Buechler, and R. J. Blakeslee, "Gridded lightning climatology from trmm-lis and otd: Dataset description," *Atmospheric Research*, vol. 135–136, pp. 404–414, 1 2014.
- [34] NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies, "2019: GISS Surface Temperature Analysis (GISTEMP), version 4," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/>
- [35] N. J. Lenssen, G. A. Schmidt, J. E. Hansen, M. J. Menne, A. Persin, R. Ruedy, and D. Zyss, "Improvements in the GISTEMP Uncertainty Model," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, vol. 124, no. 12, pp. 6307–6326, 2019.
- [36] D. Bilitza, "IRI the international standard for the ionosphere," *Advances in Radio Science*, vol. 16, pp. 1–11, 2018.